

1 **CXCL9 is silenced in metastasis to the bone in humans with prostate cancer.**

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6 Prostate cancer is among the most frequent cancers diagnosed in males and the most common site of
7 distant metastasis in humans with prostate cancer is the skeletal system (bones). We measured total
8 transcription in the pelvic metastases of humans with metastatic prostate cancer to identify gene
9 expression changes important for metastasis to the skeletal system in vivo. We identified silencing of the
10 chemokine *CXCL9* as a signature component of the bone metastatic gene expression signature in
11 metastatic prostate cancer. *CXCL9* was silenced in the central nervous system (brain) metastases of
12 humans with metastatic breast cancer. Systems biological approaches revealed transcriptional
13 co-regulation of *CXCL9* with a nuclear factor that controls the exhaustion program, *BATF2*, and a cell
14 surface receptor expressed by exhausted immune cells, *TIGIT*. *CXCL9* silencing enhances metastasis
15 because *CXCL9* levels regulate function or recruitment of cells that are exhausted, a largely impaired
16 cellular state characterized by immune dysfunction.